

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS GREEN PRODUCTS IN MANDYA CITY

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ABSTRACT:

The growing awareness of environmental issues has led to a significant shift in consumer behaviour, particularly in the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector, where the demand for green products is steadily increasing. This research explores the factors influencing consumer perception and their subsequent impact on the adoption and purchasing decisions of green products within this sector. The study on consumer perception of green products in Mandya city. It found that consumers are aware of green products and believe they are better for health and the environment, but they are often deterred by higher prices and limited availability. While a significant portion of consumers are willing to pay more for green options, they face barriers in accessibility and a lack of information, highlighting a need for better marketing, clearer eco-labels, and increased local availability.

Keywords: Consumer Perception, Green Products, FMCG Sector, Environmental Awareness, Consumer Behavior, etc.

INTRODUCTION:

In recent years, there has been a significant shift in consumer behavior towards more sustainable and eco-friendly products, driven by increasing awareness of environmental issues and a growing sense of social responsibility. Consumers are the fundamental cornerstone of every business. We consume things every day, and we also purchase these products based on our needs, preferences, and purchasing power. For marketers to fine-tune their marketing offerings and reach a high degree of customer approval and happiness, they place a great deal of significance on what consumers see, think, prefer, and purchase. Marketers now have a renewed interest in researching and comprehending rural markets as they become a viable business model. Environmental sustainability issues and environmental concerns are currently affecting and altering the consumption patterns of human existence and activities on this planet. It incorporates ideas from economics, sociology, and psychology. It makes an effort to comprehend how consumers decide, either on their own or in groups. In an effort to comprehend what people desire, it researches consumer traits such as demographics, psychographics, and behavioral variables. Additionally, it makes an effort to evaluate consumer influence from groups like family, friends, reference groups, and society at large. "Products that will not pollute the earth or deplete natural resources, and can be recycled or conserved" are characterized as "Eco-friendly products."

Green marketing refers to ecological marketing which does not pollute the environment. It is not a simple concept. It is a range of activities such as production, modifying the advertisement, changes to the production process, packaging changes etc. Green products are the products which are free of ozone-depleting chemicals, do not produce toxic products and are often made of recycled materials or content or from renewable and sustainable sources.

Green/ Eco-friendly product:

Green products are sustainable designed to minimize their environmental impact during their whole life cycle and even after they are of no use. Green products are usually identified as having two basic goals: reducing waste and minimizing resource efficiency. They are manufactured by using toxic free ingredients and environmentally producers and are certified by recognized organizations like Energy Star, Forest Stewardship Council etc.

Examples: bamboo toothbrush, bio degradable carry bag, reusable water bottles etc.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The current study on the attitudes of consumers toward buying environmentally friendly products in Mandya sheds insight on those attitudes. Numerous studies that concentrate on various facets of growth, awareness marketing, and sustainability have been undertaken all around the world. A review of literature is an overview of primarily published works on a specific topic. In this topic there are various research articles, theses etc... Some of them are reviewed to move further in this study. They are as follows:

Mainieri (1997) made study on "The Environmental Study". Define Eco-friendly products as ecologically safe products that can facilitate the long-term goal of protecting and preserving our natural habitat. Pickett-Baker & Ozaki (2008) suggest that eco-friendly products should be supplied by companies with a reputation for reducing environmental impacts from their manufacturing processes.

Chitra (2007) made study on "Green Global Study" the need for eco-friendly products is gradually increasing on account of a persistent rise in cancer for environmental related issues. Fortunately, eco-friendly consumption and spending patterns have led the marketers to understand the Eco-friendly attitude of the consumers and came up with the marketing mix which preserves environmental resources and at the same time delivers value-added products and services.

Preeti Sehgal (2010) made study on "Impact of Eco-Friendly Products on Consumer Behavior" has made an attempt to examine the make consumers aware, environmentally friendly goods and services often are marked with eco-labels. The study used Primary Data. The study found that the introduction of green as a considered attribute at the point of sale, enables consumers to comparison shop based on green. The study argued suggested that environmentally friendly products are good for humans and nature. Some environmentally friendly products are more costly than traditional types of products but savings can be made if we go back-to-basics.

Peattie (2012) made a study on "green marketing and green purchasing behavior". Concluded that those who avoid products that are likely to affect the health of the consumer or others, cause significant damage to the environment during manufacturing, use, or disposal, consume a disproportionate amount of energy, cause unnecessary waste, use materials derived from threatened species of the environment.

Suresh (2013) made study on "impact of eco-friendly products on consumer behavior". The study identified that the usually all people are influenced by eco-friendly products. This product is not easily available in market, and eco-friendly products are costly hence consumer move away from it. Nowadays, family decisions are vital in purchasing decisions.

Statement of the problem:-

Now a days most of the consumers are moving towards eco-friendly products rather than using of the conventional products. The purpose of the study is to know the consumers' perception towards green products and to know the factors which force the consumers to move towards purchase of green products. To earn more profit, most companies harm the environment and later they build the concern about the environment and the health of consumers, so the companies find a new way of making money. The first problem for companies is finding out the needs, wants, consumers' tastes and preferences and lifestyle of consumers because the needs and wants are unlimited The second problem is that most of the consumers are illiterate and they do not have awareness of green products.

Need for study :-

The concept of green products has emerged around the world due to the side effects of the chemical-contented products. This leads to a significant impact on the health of the people and environment. This study helps to examine the consumer's perception and demographic factors of the consumers which influence purchase of products.

Research gap :-

After reviewing the existing literature, it is found that there are few studies on the consumer perception towards green products. On the other hand, it is found that there are no specific studies on consumers' perceptions towards green products in Mandya city, which gives rise to studying the same in order to fill the gap

Objectives of the Study:-

1. To examine the awareness level of consumers towards green products.
2. To analyse the consumer's perception towards green products.
3. To evaluate the factors influencing the buying behaviour of customers towards green products.
4. To analyse the problems faced by consumers while purchasing green products

Research methodology:-

The present study is purely descriptive as it analyses, describes, and evaluates the data related to the consumers' perception of green products.

1. Source of data collection - This study is based on primary data and secondary data.

- Primary data: The data is collected through a survey of the consumers using a wellstructured questionnaire
- Secondary data: Has been used to gather information from published books, journals,articles, newspapers, websites etc....

2. Sample and population

The target population for this research is consumers like students, employees and senior citizens who belong to the Mandya city. From the above population, by using a convenient sampling method, 100 respondents are selected for collection of data.

Data analysis and interpretation:-

Table - 1			
GENDER			
SL.No.	Gender	No observation	Percentage (%)
1	Male	30	30
2	Female	70	70
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 30% of respondents were male and 70% of respondents were female who have given their opinion about this study.

Table - 2			
GENDER			
SL.No.	Age Group	No observation	Percentage (%)
1	15-20	10	10
2	20-25	90	90
3	25-30	0	0
4	Above 30	0	0
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 10% of respondents belong to the age group of 15 – 20 years, 90% of respondents belong to the age group of 20 – 25 years.

Table - 3			
EDUCATION			
SL.No.	Education Qualification	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	BELOW GRADUATION	16	16
2	UG	64	64
3	PG	10	10
4	Other	10	10
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Table - 4			
OCCUPATION			
SL.No.	Particular	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	Student	44	44
2	Employees	34	34
3	Business Man	18	18
4	Other	4	4
Total		100	100

Analysis:

In this study out of 100 respondents 16 % are below graduation ,64% have completed their Under Graduate, 10% have completed post-graduation, 10% completed their Others.

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:

In this study, out of 100 respondents, it is very clear that 44% of respondents are students and 34% of respondents are employees, 18% of respondent Business Man and 4% of respondent are Others.

Table - 5			
Income Level			
SL.No.	Income per Month	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	Below Rs.10000	36	36
2	Rs.10000 to Rs.20000	28	28
3	Rs.20000 to Rs.30000	26	26
4	Above Rs.30000	10	10
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:-

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 36% of respondents had Rs.10,000 per month, 28% of respondents had Rs.10,000 – Rs.20,000 per month and 26% of respondents had Rs.20000 – Rs 30000 and 10% of respondent are above 30,000 income per month.

Table - 6			
Level of awareness about green products			
SL.No.	Particulars	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	Aware about It and Used IT	76	76
2	Hering about It for the First Time	16	16
3	Heard about It but never used	8	8
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:-

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 76% of respondents are aware of green products & also use them, 16% of respondents heard about it but never used it, 08% of respondents hearing about it for the first time.

Table - 7			
Source of information			
SL.No.	Source of Information	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	Friends and Family	29	29
2	Advertisement	12	12

3	Social Media	56	56
4	Others	3	3
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Analysis:-

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 56% of respondents are aware of the source of social media, 29% of respondents are aware of the source of friends & family, 12% of respondents are aware by advertisement & 3% of respondents are aware from other source.

Table - 8			
Preference of Green Products			
SL.No.	Types of Eco-Friendly Product	No of observation	Percentage (%)
1	Personal care Product	28	28
2	Cosmetics Product	8	8
3	Carry Bags	48	48
4	House hold essentials	16	16
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Source

Inference

In this study, out of 100 respondents, 48% of respondents prefer green carry bags, 28% of respondents prefer personal care products, 16% of respondents prefer the household essentials and 8% of respondents prefers cosmetics.

Findings:-

1. In the 100 respondents, 30% of respondents were male and 70% of respondents were females who gave their opinion about this study. It is found that most of the respondents are female.
2. In the out of 100 respondents, 10% of respondents belong to the age group of 15 – 20 years, 90% of respondents belong to the age group of 20 – 25 years. The majority of respondents belong to the age group of 20 to 25.
3. In the out of 100 respondents, 16 % are below graduation, 10% have completed their post graduation ,64% completed their under graduation. It is observed that most of all the respondents are under graduated.
4. In the out of 100 respondents, it is very clear that 44% of respondents are students and 34% of respondents are employees .It is found that the majority of respondents are students.
5. In the out of 100 respondents, 36% of respondents had Rs.10,000 per month ,28% of respondents had Rs.10,000 – Rs.20,000 per month, 26% of respondent had Rs.20000 – Rs.30000 and 10% of respondents had Rs.30,000 and above income per month. It is observed that most of the respondents' income is below Rs.10,000 per month.
6. In the out of 100 respondents, 56% of respondents are aware of the source of social media, 29% of respondents are aware of the source of friends & family, 12% of

respondents are aware by advertisement & 3% of respondents are aware of other source. It is found that most of the respondents are aware of green products through the source of social media.

SUGGESTIONS:-

1. There is a lack of demand for green products because of lack of awareness, so, governments or organizations can take a step to create awareness programmers.
2. The government should mandate all companies to produce green products.
3. The purchase opinion of consumers towards green products is good, but there is a lack of demand because of lack of availability so the government should use a good technical mechanism to improve the availability.
4. The companies which are producing green products should give more eco label on the product, because to attract or grasp the attention of customer.
5. Companies should give more advertisements or should promote more green products on social media.
6. Companies should design their distribution system in such a way that products remain available all the time in rural areas, because rural customers prefer green products which are easily available.
7. The majority of the respondents' opinion is environmental that issues are only gimmicks for commercial purposes, so, companies should educate customers on environmental protection.
8. Green products should be priced according to their quality.
9. There should not be a price difference between standard products and green products.
10. Green product quality should be better than commercial products quality.

CONCLUSION:-

The present paper concludes that the success of many businesses depends on their ability to create and retain customers. Companies to sell their products at a standard price with good quality, availability of branded products in all stores and it should be less costly to attract new customers. The purpose of this study is to understand the awareness level green product and factors that influence to purchase green product such as eco knowledge, price sensitivity, environmental concern, social influence, changing life style etc. It has been observed from the analysis that people think green products are good for the environment and also healthy for the environment and society as well. Green products are better than conventional products. But these products' availability is low due to the lack of demand for green products. Consumers are aware of green products and they have a positive perception towards green products. It was found that lack of knowledge and lack of awareness of the benefits are barriers to purchasing green products. The majority of respondents buy green products for health purposes and they are concerned about the environment too. Thus, I can conclude that the government should strengthen its efforts in informing the public about the safety issues and policies related to the concept green by exploring mass and social media. In addition, government authorities should put their efforts into promotion and consumers' positive perception towards green products.

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